

A coupled field finite element model to predict actuation properties of piezoelectrically actuated bistable composites.

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SUMMARY

This paper presents the development and validation of a coupled-field finite element model to predict the response of a piezoelectrically actuated bistable laminate for structural morphing applications. Derivation of materials properties and validation of piezoelectric actuator model against experimental data are described. The model shows qualitative agreement with experimental results.

Keywords: Bistability, piezoelectric actuation, finite element, structural morphing

Introduction

The use of smart structures in the design of morphing aerofoil sections has been proposed as a key future technology in the aerospace industry[1]. One approach to generating the large deformations necessary for aerospace applications is the use of bistable composite laminates with embedded piezoelectric actuation[2]. Residual thermal stresses created during post-cure cooling cause multistable laminates to be structurally stable in two or more shapes at room temperature[3]. An actuation load may be applied by a piezoelectric actuator to switch the laminate between structurally stable shapes without requiring continuous power supply to maintain that new shape.

By integrating these bistable laminates within a larger structure novel morphing structures may be created [4, 5]. These structures present significant challenges to current analytical models of bistable laminates. To date analytical models have been unable to accurately predict the actuation properties of piezoelectrically actuated bistable laminates. Analyses including embedded actuation have been possible only for rectangular laminates[6], and have failed to accurately capture experimentally observed behaviour.

Analytical tools remain of interest as their ability to rapidly explore a design space remain superior to Finite Element (FE) simulation, however the complex interactions with supporting structures and varying arrangements of actuators remain insoluble with purely analytical methods. FE analysis provides a tool for analysing these more complex structures, and as such robust models of constituent parts become necessary.

FE modelling of piezoelectric actuators has been widely implemented in a diverse range of fields with excellent agreement with experiment, however to date no well founded study has been conducted relating to bistable laminates; previous investigations within this field have used inappropriate element types [7] or made use of incomplete piezoelectric material properties[8].

In this paper a FE model will be described that accurately models the stiffness $[s_{ij}]$, piezoelectric constants $[d_{ij}]$ and relative electrical permittivity $[\epsilon_{ij}]$ of a commonly used piezoelectric actuator. The actuator model is validated against experimental data for an actuated aluminium beam under varying electrical boundary conditions. This novel validation step allows the electro-mechanical coupling to be more fully investigated than in previous studies.

Model Formulation

The modelling detailed in the following sections was undertaken using the commercially available software Ansys V11 using 20-node coupled-field solid elements (SOLID226). Element aspect ratio within the MFC volume was 3.33 for all models.

Stiffness Matrix Formulation

The active portion of the MFC was modelled as a homogenous solid in order to create a functional representation of the actuator. A detailed model of the construction of the MFC was deemed inappropriate as its inclusion in a macro scale model of the actuated composite would increase computation time. This approach aims to accurately capture the relationship between the stress field imposed on the laminate by the MFC under both applied electric field and passive deformation with varying electric boundary conditions.

This functional representation of the mechanical properties of the MFC was achieved by converting the four linear elastic engineering constants presented in Table 1 into the stiffness matrix $[s_{ij}]$ for a transversely isotropic material (i.e. one with a single axis of rotational symmetry, the poling direction in PZT fibres). The stiffness Matrix was populated by substituting the values in Table 1 into equation 1, derived from the standard stress-strain relations presented in [9].

Table 1 Mechanical properties of Smart Materials Corp M8557 MFC actuator taken from [10] and manufacturers data sheet[11].

	Williams et al 2004.	Smart Materials M8557 MFC
E_{33} (GPa)	29.4	30.336
E_{11} (GPa)	15.2	15.857
G_{31} (GPa)	6.06	5.515
ν_{31}	0.312	0.31
ν_{13}	0.16	0.16

$$[s_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_3} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{31}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu_{31})}{E_3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu_{31})}{E_3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where E is the Young's modulus, G the shear modulus, ν the Poisson's ratio of the material and subscripts denote the orientation of each property. The poling-direction of the MFC is denoted as the 3-direction and is aligned with the longitudinal fibre-axis, the 1-direction in the models coordinate system as in Fig. 1

Fig. 1: Orientation of MFC material coordinate system.

The three dimensional stiffness matrix was validated by solving a structural model of the actuator under an applied mechanical stress of 1Pa, with FE-predicted strains agreeing exactly with those calculated using manufacturers values for the linear elastic constants.

Piezoelectric Matrix Formulation

As described by several investigators the relationships between the piezoelectric properties of the constituent materials and the complete MFC are highly complex and still subject of research efforts [12, 13]. With this in mind effective piezoelectric constants for the device were determined in order to describe the average response of the MFC to an applied electric field.

Previous work by Williams *et al.* [13] experimentally determined the free-strain behaviour of the same MFC actuator used in the present study. The value for d_{33} presented in [13] matches closely with data presented by the manufacturer[11], however, no value for d_{31} is reported by either source. In the same work, Williams *et al.* determined d_{33} and d_{31} values for a similar Active Fibre Composite device, construction and mode of operation are sufficiently similar between the AFC and MFC devices to

assume the d_{33}/d_{31} ratio to be equal in both devices [6]. The piezoelectric constants for the MFC are presented in Table 2 along with the values for relative electrical permittivity [ϵ_{ij}].

Table 2 Piezoelectric stress constants [d_{ij}] and relative electrical permittivity of MFC.

	Smart Materials Corp M8557 MFC actuator
d_{33} (pm/V)	467
d_{32} (pm/V)	-233
d_{31} (pm/V)	-233
ϵ_1^s	23.6
ϵ_2^s	9.1
ϵ_3^s	746.3

Permittivity Matrix Formulation

In order to fully couple the elastic and electric fields within the MFC model, the relative electrical permittivity of the device was determined. The influence of permittivity is demonstrated in the differing responses of piezoelectric devices in which no induced electric field is permitted (closed circuit) and those where an induced field may occur (open circuit). The field strength developed by a unit force is governed by:

$$E = \frac{Ad_{33}}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_3 D} \quad (2)$$

where A is the charge-collecting area, D is the separation of the two charge-collecting surfaces, d_{33} the piezoelectric stress constant, E is induce field strength, ϵ_0 the permittivity of free space and ϵ_3 the relative electrical permittivity. Hence, permittivity is vital in understanding the response of piezoelectric devices subjected to any form of mechanical loading.

In order to determine the relative electrical permittivity under constant stress a simple test was under taken within the FE environment. A $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{mm}^3$ cube of the MFC model was created and subjected to a unit electric field while constrained in the 3-direction only; this constraint produced a stress proportional to the applied field according d_{33} . Rearranging the piezoelectric constitutive equations [14] an expression for the permittivity at constant strain (ϵ_3^s) was derived:

$$\epsilon_3^s = \frac{d_{33} \sigma_3}{\epsilon_0} \quad (3)$$

to give the values of permittivity presented in Table 2.

Model validation

The MFC's actuation properties as well as its response to mechanical loading under varying electrical boundary conditions were experimentally characterised in order to validate the FE-model. MFC actuators were bonded to top and bottom surface of an aluminium beam using araldite two-part epoxy as in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Experimental setup with aluminium beam, the driven actuator (MFC-1), the passive actuator (MFC-2) with dimensions shown in millimetres.

The beam was then clamped as in Fig. 2 so that beam deflection was not influenced by gravitational forces. A Nippon LAS5010v laser displacement sensor with a resolution of $10\mu\text{m}$ was used to measure deflection, with measurements coupled to drive voltage through an analogue data-logger. The active MFC was driven from a signal generator with an attached Trek PZD700 Piezodriver.

To standardise creep effects in MFC response, all measurements were taken after a 60 second settling period. Closed circuit boundary conditions were imposed on the passive MFC by electrically connecting the two electrode terminals, thus preventing a potential drop between electrodes. Open circuit boundary conditions was created by insulating both electrode terminals.

Results

Beam deflection as a function of MFC drive-voltage is presented in Fig. 3 and clearly shows the linear trend predicted by engineering beam theory {gere1997}. Predicted values agreed with experimental values to within 2%, it should be noted that for all, except the value for 160V, the error was within measurement uncertainty of $\pm 10\mu\text{m}$. The close agreement between FE and experimental data suggests that the linear model of MFC piezoelectric properties presented here is sufficient to model actuated structures.

Fig. 3: Beam deflection as a function of MFC drive-voltage.

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show beam deflection (D_y) as a function of distance from the clamp for an MFC-1 drive voltage of 400V with MFC-2 under open and closed circuit boundary conditions respectively. FE-predictions of D_y are accurate to within 6% compared with experimental values for both conditions. The anomalous deflection of the beam at 160mm was found to be due to surface defect present before testing.

Prediction of closed circuit behaviour overestimated deflection, while open circuit deflection was underestimated. It is also important to note that the relative decrease in deflection between open and closed circuit boundary conditions predicted was greater than that observed in experiment. These two factors indicate that the estimated values for ϵ_3 were too small and confirm the need for experimental measurement of ϵ_3 to fully predict MFC behaviour.

Fig. 4: Beam deflection as a function of z-position with MFC-2 under open circuit boundary conditions.

Fig. 5: Beam deflection as a function of z position with MFC-2 under closed circuit boundary conditions.

Conclusions

This paper has developed a finite element model of a commercially available MFC actuator by aggregating mechanical, piezoelectric and permittivity properties to form a representative homogeneous solid model. This functional model allows effective representation of the composite and predicts MFC behaviour under a range of mechanical and electrical loading schemes.

Electro-mechanical coupling has been accurately defined by specifying the relative electrical permittivity matrix $[\epsilon_{ij}]$. Model predictions of actuation performance have been validated against experimental data and are accurate to within 6%.

The change in load-deflection behaviour of a structure including passive MFCs has been predicted with excellent agreement with experimental measurements. The variation in load-deflection behaviour caused by under variation in MFC electrical boundary conditions is also accurately modeled. The proposed homogeneous solid model provides accurate functional representation of an MFC for modelling of smart structures.

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